

The Effect of Motivation and Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Their Impact on the Performance of Village Unit Cooperative Employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The Village Unit Cooperative (VUC) in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency is an organization engaged in all-round business, such as trading of palm oil fresh fruit bunches. The VUC serves as a partner and partner of several oil palm plantation companies. Results Based on the annual accountability report, the achievement of profit targets has decreased, as well as decreased discipline levels based on the results of the list of absenteeism and employee tardiness. This study is intended to examine the influence, work discipline, and organizational culture on job satisfaction and its impact on the performance of the village unit cooperative employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency. The population in this study were all permanent employees of VUC as many as 191 people, with a sample of 130 people using purposive sampling technique. The research method used is a verification method (causal study) with data collection using Interview and questionnaire techniques, which are then processed using Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM-PLS). The results of this study indicate that motivation has a significant effect on job satisfaction and performance, work discipline has a significant effect on job satisfaction but has no effect on performance, then organizational culture has a significant effect on job satisfaction, but has no effect on performance, and finally job satisfaction shows a significant effect on job satisfaction performance of VUC employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency.

KEYWORDS: Performance, Motivation, Work Discipline, Organizational Culutre

I. INTRODUCTION

Indeed a company in consists of various kinds of individuals belonging to various characters and statuses, thus human resources need to be managed properly and professionally, so that the organization creates a balance between the needs of human resources can be achieved with business progress. This balance as one of the main keys for the organization to be able to develop and grow productively and naturally, the organization is very dependent on the performance of human resources in the organization, forward to produce good performance, it is necessary in the organization to pay attention to motivation, discipline and a good work culture, as an important point to continue to be developed. The importance of good performance results from each individual in an organization will be able to provide a sustainable positive point for a company organization. As stated by Armstrong and Baron, in Mangkunegara (2013) that performance is the result of work that has a strong relationship with organizational strategic goals. Furthermore, it is explained that there are many factors that affect the performance of employees in an organization, such as motivation, discipline, and work culture. Through these factors, in general, they should be able to produce proper job satisfaction and good work results. Where through job satisfaction will form a positive performance, as stated by Greenberg in (Wibowo, 2013) that job satisfaction is described as a positive or negative attitude that is done by individuals towards their work. In every organization or company it will continue to be sustainable, as well as in Village Unit Cooperative (VUC).

The Village Unit Cooperative (VUC) in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency is an organization engaged in all-round business which consists of buying and selling fresh fruit bunches of oil palm, savings and loans, sales of motor vehicle spare parts, and heavy equipment rental. Of the several business fields that remain active and continue to operate well, the VUC is engaged in the trade business of fresh fruit bunches of oil palm, where the VUC is a mentor and partner of several oil palm plantation companies. In general,

The Effect of Motivation and Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Their Impact on the Performance of Village Unit Cooperative Employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Indonesia

this VUC has implemented well the job description and the leadership is well implemented, as a form of maintaining and developing the organization. However, based on general observations, if you look deeper, it can be seen that the motivation of some employees seems to be decreasing, the way of completing work is late, lack of accuracy, and through task completion there is a decrease in the form of cooperation, so that the existing culture is seen to have changed. Through these problems it appears that job satisfaction is not in accordance with what it should be, even though the organization tries to provide efforts to improve performance results with the addition of promotional facilities, but it appears that the results obtained have not been able to produce the targets that have been set, in the VUC organization every year. will target the profit that has been determined in accordance with the cooperative's revenue and expenditure budget plan of 80% from each previous year. The following is a table for achieving VUC targets in the Table. 1

Table 1. Achievement of Village Unit Cooperative Target

No	Achievement of Village Unit Cooperative Target				
	VUC	Previous Year's Profit	Targets	Achievement of Targets	Achievement
1	Surya Adi	154.840.000	80%	122.000.000	78.79%
2	Surya Bakti	169.764.000	80%	133.980.000	78.92%
3	Marga Mulya	187.205.000	80%,	148.000.000	79.06%
	Sinar Jaya	109.704.000	80%	94.000.000	85.69%

Source: Accountability Report 2019 – 2021

It can be seen from the table above where the achievement of the target decreases from the planned revenue and expenditure budget that has been set as the target. This means that in VUC there is a problem that triggers the non-achievement of the target. In addition to inappropriate achievements, it is clear that employee discipline has also decreased, which can be seen from the employee absentee list per/January to June, following the list of absenteeism and delays of VUC employees:

Table 2. Employee Absence and Late List Village Unit Cooperative Januari – June

Month	Absence (person)				Amount	Tardiness (person)				Amount
	SA	SB	MM	SJ		SA	SB	MM	SJ	
January	1	0	2	1	4	2	2	1	3	8
February	0	0	2	3	5	3	3	1	2	9
March	2	1	0	3	6	2	0	1	1	4
April	1	1	0	1	3		2	4	2	8
May	2	0	1	0	3	2	3	3	2	10
June	0	0	0	2	2	3	2	2	2	9
July	0	1	1	1	3	4	0	0	3	7
August	1	0	2	0	3	2	2	2	0	6
September	3	1	0	0	4	1	3	2	0	6
October	0	1	0	2	3	3	3	0	2	8
November	2	0	0	0	2	2	2	0	3	7
December	3	0	1	1	5	3	0	1	1	5

Source: Village Unit Cooperative Personnel division, 2021

From the table above, it can be seen that it fluctuates and almost occurs every month. Most of the absences (absenteeism) of employees occurred in March, which amounted to 6 person, and the most delays occurred in May, which amounted to 10 person. In addition, several employees also mentioned that it is often the case that employees who arrive late get an unpleasant welcome from other employees so that employees who come late are not optimal at work. This condition will lead to ineffectiveness and inefficiency in a person's work, and further can reduce performance. Based on the description of the

The Effect of Motivation and Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Their Impact on the Performance of Village Unit Cooperative Employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Indonesia

background above, in this case the author tries to do research by seeing whether the theories presented are in accordance with the results of observations in general in accordance with the actual situation, with the title The Effect of Motivation, Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Their Impact on the Performance of Village Unit Cooperative Employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

Performance is the result of work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him based on skills, experience, sincerity of time, (Hasibuan 2016). Furthermore, the implementation of performance is carried out by human resources who have the ability, competence, motivation, and interests (Wibowo, 2013). In performance there are factors that can affect a person's performance such as; (1) Personality, which is related to one's character (2) Job satisfaction, is a feeling of pleasure or liking before and after doing work (3) Work discipline, as an employee's effort to carry out his work activities seriously. (4) Work motivation, as an encouragement for someone who is strong from within himself or from outside. (5) Organizational Culture, as a prevailing habit or norm owned by an organization. Furthermore, a performance indicator can be measured by looking at the quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness, independence and work commitment.

Job Satisfaction

Satisfaction refers to the level of fulfillment of needs, wants, and desires. Wexly and Yuki (2011) explain that job satisfaction is a person's feeling of work based on an evaluation of the perceived aspects of the job. This attitude describes a pleasant or unpleasant experience and expectations about future experiences. Job satisfaction is a positive attitude of employees towards the work they face and all things related to the job, such as; (1) Increased productivity and work performance. (2) Increase work morale. (3) Reducing absenteeism. (4) Increase work motivation. (5) creates a positive attitude towards his work. Robinso and Comers in Zuhdin (2016) mention that job satisfaction will provide benefits in increasing life happiness, productivity, achievement and reducing repair costs. The indicators of employee job satisfaction according to Robbins (2012) are: (1) Supportive working conditions (2) Adequate salary or wages (3) Supportive coworkers.

Motivation

Motivation is the provision of a driving force that creates one's work enthusiasm so that they want to work together, work effectively, and be integrated with all efforts for achievement (Hasibuan, 2016). Factors that affect motivation are divided into two, namely internally and externally, (Sutrisno, 2015). Motivation aims to encourage enthusiasm, increase morale, increase productivity, maintain loyalty, improve discipline, streamline employee procurement, create good working relationships, increase creativity, increase a sense of responsibility and increase efficiency in the use of tools. The indicators of work motivation according to Uno (2011) are grouped into two, namely internal and external.

Working Discipline

Work discipline is an attitude of respect for the rules and regulations of the company that exist within the employee, which can cause him to conform voluntarily to the company's rules and regulations (Sutrisno, 2015). Indicators of work discipline include; (1) Goals and capabilities. (2) Leader's example. (3) Repayment. (4) Justice. (5) Waskat. (6) Penalty sanction. (7) firmness. (8) Human relations. (Kasmir, 2016).

Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a collective agreement about shared values in organizational life and binds everyone in the organization concerned. In organizational culture the same perception among all members of the organization about the true meaning of life together, (Siagian 2014). Furthermore, according to Victor in Wibowo (2013) that organizational culture is a way of doing things in an organization. In organizational culture there are several characteristics such as; innovation and risk taking, attention to detail, result oriented, human/team/aggressive oriented, stability. Benefits of organizational culture; (1) Help direct human resources to achieve the vision, mission, and goals of the organization. (2) Increasing cohesiveness between teams, various departments, divisions, or units. (3) Shaping staff behavior. (4) Increase staff motivation. (5) Can improve behavior. Indicators of organizational culture according to Mckenna (2005) are; (1) The relationship between humans and humans. (2) Cooperation. (3) Employee appearance.

The Effect of Motivation and Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Their Impact on the Performance of Village Unit Cooperative Employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Indonesia

Previous Research

Table 3. Previous Research

Researcher's Name	Title of Research	Research purposes	Research Results
K Utami (2016)	The Effect of Motivation and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at the Graha Arthama Cooperative in Nganjuk	Analyze the effect of motivation, the effect of job satisfaction, on the performance of employees of the Graha Arthamas cooperative in Nganjuk	Motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance, motivation has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction, job satisfaction has a positive and significant impact on performance.
Aini K N & Ariefiantoro T (2018)	The Influence of Motivation Work, Environment Work, Discipline Work and Stress Work on Employee Performance at PT. Nusantara IX Plantation Semarang	To determine the effect of work motivation, work environment, work discipline and work stress on employee performance at PT. Nusantara IX Plantation Semarang	There is an effect of work motivation, work environment, work discipline and work stress on employee performance at PT. Nusantara IX Plantation Semarang
M. A. H Kadir (2017)	Effect of Work Motivation, Compensation, Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance of the Ministry of Manpower	To determine the effect of work motivation and job satisfaction on employee performance as well as the effect of work discipline on employee performance.	Motivation work has no effect on job satisfaction, compensation has no effect on job satisfaction, organizational culture has no effect on job satisfaction, work motivation does not affect employee performance, compensation has no effect on employee performance, organizational culture affects employee performance and job satisfaction affects employee performance
M Agustian (2017)	The influence of motivation, work discipline work environment on the performance of employees of PT. Nur Medinah Intermedia	To determine the effect of motivation, work discipline work environment on the performance of employees of PT. Nur Medinah Intermedia	There is the influence of motivation, work discipline and work environment simultaneously and partially on employee performance. PT. Nur Medinah Intermedia

Source: Various Research Results

Hypothesis

Hypothesis testing criteria can be done by looking at the p-value. When the p-value is less than alpha 0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted, if it is less than alpha 0.05 then the hypothesis is rejected. Another test criterion is the level of significance: H_0 is rejected if $|t \text{ statistic}| > t_{\alpha, df}$ or $p\text{-value} < . S$. Based on the framework of thought, the formulation of the hypothesis in this research is as follows;

1. There is an influence of motivation on job satisfaction of employees of the village cooperative unit in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency.
2. There is an effect of work discipline on job satisfaction of village cooperative unit employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency.
3. There is an influence of organizational culture on job satisfaction of village cooperative unit employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency.
4. There is an influence of motivation on the performance of village unit cooperative employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency.

The Effect of Motivation and Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Their Impact on the Performance of Village Unit Cooperative Employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Indonesia

5. There is an effect of work discipline on the performance of village unit cooperative employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency.
6. There is an influence of organizational culture on the performance of village unit cooperative employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency.
7. There is an effect of job satisfaction on employee performance at the village unit cooperative in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency.

III. METHOD

The research method used by the author is a verification method (causal study) which is used to examine the relationship between exogenous variables: Motivation (1), Work Discipline (E2), Organizational Culture (E3) and endogenous variables namely Job Satisfaction (η1) and Performance (η2). The population in this study were all permanent employees of the Village Unit Cooperative (VUC) in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency who were engaged in the trade business of oil palm fresh fruit bunches, as many as 191 people, with sampling using the Slovin formula producing 130 people who will be the sample, using purposive sampling technique, namely by determining certain criteria (Sujarweni, 2019). With data collection methods using interview techniques (Interview) and Questionnaires, which will then use Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM-PLS), with reference to Ghozali, I. & Latan, H. (2015) as a data testing method. SEM-PLS is used to analyze the relationship between endogenous and exogenous variables, endogenous and endogenous, and the relationship between manifest or indicators.

IV. RESULT

Descriptions or general descriptions of respondents in this study include gender, education, and age of employees. Based on the respondents based on gender, there were 95 or 73, 1% men and 35 people or 26, 9% women. Characteristics of respondents based on education level, namely high school as many as 94 people or 72.3%, Diploma 7 people or 5.4%, Bachelor degree 29 people or 22.3%, Postgraduate 0% and Doctoral 0%. Furthermore, based on the age of the respondents, it can be seen that most of them are aged between 31-35 years as many as 63 people, 42 people aged 25-30, 22 people aged 36-40 and at least 41-42 are 3 people. This study, the instrument test consisted of validity and reliability tests using 130 samples. The results of the measurement model (outer model) to test the validity and reliability, the coefficient of determination of the model and the path coefficient for the equation model, can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 1. Measurement Model – Outer Model

Validity testing is carried out with a convergent validity test, assessed from the loading factor for each construct indicator. The loading factor value is the correlation between item scores and construct scores. The recommended loading factor value is above 0, or above 0.6. In addition, an indicator is considered valid as well, when the indicator has an AVE (average variance extracted) value above 0.5. The AVE value is the average percentage score of the variance extracted from the latent variable.

The Effect of Motivation and Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Their Impact on the Performance of Village Unit Cooperative Employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Indonesia

Through the picture above, it can be seen that the loading factor value on motivation, work discipline, organizational culture, job satisfaction has a value above 0.6, which means that all criteria are declared valid.

In this study, the reliability test was carried out by using the composite reliability test, to measure the real value of the reliability of a construct. A construct or variable is said to be reliable if it gives an Alpha value > 0.7 and Composite Reliability > 0.7. In the picture above, it can be seen that each latent variable shows that the composite reliability value is greater than 0.7, which means that all variables are reliable and have met the test criteria.

Inferential Statistical Analysis - Structural Model (Structural Model) - Inner Model

The structural model (inner model) was evaluated using R2 for endogenous variables and path coefficients for exogenous variables which were then assessed for significance based on the t-statistics value of each path. The structural model of this research can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 2. Structural Model with Bootstrapping Procedure

In the figure above, it can be seen the significance of the prediction model in structural model testing, it can be seen from the value of t-statistics between exogenous variables to endogenous variables, which is described in detail in the Path Coefficient Table of the SmartPLS output results below:

Table 4. Path Coefficient

Variable Laten	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T- Statistics	P - Values	Signifikansi
Motivation->Job Satisfaction	0.961	0.285	3.375	0.001	Significant
Motivation->Performance	0.588	0.199	2.952	0.003	Significant
Work Discipline->Job Satisfaction	1.509	0.543	2.779	0.66	Significant
Work Discipline->Performance	0.313	0.368	0.849	0.396	Not Significant
Org Culture->Job Satisfaction	1.405	0.409	3.436	0.001	Significant
Org Culture->Performance	0.369	0.267	1.379	0.168	Not Significant
Job Satisfaction->Performance	0.267	0.082	3.247	0.001	Significant

Source: Data processed by 2022 researchers

Through Table 4 is used to assess the test of direct effects (direct effects) between latent variables. Through the table above, the results of the hypothesis in this study can be seen as follows:

Hypothesis Testing 1: The Effect of Motivation on Job Satisfaction

In table 4 it can be seen that the original sample estimate value of motivation to job satisfaction is 0.961 with a significance of 5% which is indicated by the t-statistic value of 3.375 which is greater than the t-table value of 1.96. The original sample

The Effect of Motivation and Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Their Impact on the Performance of Village Unit Cooperative Employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Indonesia

estimate value is positive which indicates that motivation has a positive effect on performance. Based on these results, the first hypothesis is accepted. The results of this first hypothesis study are in line with research conducted by K Utami (2016), and M A H Kadir (2017) where motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction for employees, at the Graha Arthanama Cooperative in Nganjuk and on employees of the Ministry of Manpower. From the results of this study and previous research, it means that this is in line with the theory presented by (Hasibuan 2016) that motivation is the driving force that creates work enthusiasm so that they are willing to work together, be effective and integrated with all efforts for achievement. Through the theory and the results of this study, it means that of course motivation is very necessary in job satisfaction for employees.

Hypothesis Testing 2: The Influence of Work Discipline on Job Satisfaction

The results of the test in table 4 can be seen that the original sample estimate of work discipline on job satisfaction is 1.509 with a significance of 5%, which is indicated by the t-statistic value of 2.779 which is greater than the t-table value of 1.96. The value of the original sample estimate is positive which indicates that work discipline has a positive effect on job satisfaction. Based on these results, the second hypothesis is accepted. The positive effect of work discipline on job satisfaction is of course an answer that in an organization it is important to apply work discipline so that it can provide satisfaction for employees at work. As the theory conveyed by (Sutrisno, 2015) that work discipline is an attitude of respect for the rules and regulations of a company organization that is instilled in employees, meaning that when discipline can be implemented properly, satisfaction at work will be obtained.

Hypothesis Testing 3: The Influence of Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction

The results of the test in table 4 can be seen that the original sample estimate value of organizational culture on job satisfaction is 1.405 with a significance of 5%, which is indicated by the t-statistic value of 3.436 which is greater than the t-table value of 1.96. The value of the original sample estimate is positive which indicates that organizational culture has a positive effect on job satisfaction. Based on these results, the third hypothesis is accepted. The positive effect and acceptance of the hypothesis of organizational culture on job satisfaction in this study is not in line with the research produced by M.A. H. Kadir (2017) where organizational culture has no effect on employee job satisfaction at the Ministry of Manpower. Meaning that to be able to see whether or not an organizational culture has an effect on job satisfaction, of course, one has to look at the overall conditions in the organizational environment.

Hypothesis Testing 4: The Influence of Motivation on Performance

The results of the test in table 4 can be seen that the original sample estimate of motivation to performance is 0.588 with a significance of 5% which is indicated by the t-statistic value of 2.951 which is greater than the t-table value of 1.96. The original sample estimate value is positive which indicates that motivation has a positive effect on performance. Based on these results, the fourth hypothesis is accepted. The significance and acceptance of the motivational hypothesis on performance in this study is in line with the results of research conducted by K Utami (2016), M Agustian (2017), and Aini K N and Ariefiantoro (2018). But not with the results of research conducted by M A H Kadir (2017) where in his research states that work motivation has no effect on employee performance at the Ministry of Manpower. Judging from some previous research and the results of this study mean that motivation as a driving force to create enthusiasm in one's work must be seen from two internal and external indicators so that maximum results can be seen in the assessment.

Hypothesis Testing 5: The Effect of Work Discipline on Performance

The results of the test in table 4 can be seen that the original sample estimate of work discipline on performance is 0.313 with a significance of 5% which is indicated by the t-statistic value of 0.849 which is smaller than the t-table value of 1.96. Based on these results, the fifth hypothesis is rejected. It has no effect and the rejection of the work discipline hypothesis on performance means that even though there is a delay in entering working hours, it certainly cannot determine how a person's performance results. The results of this study are not in line with the results of research conducted by M Agustian (2017), and Aini KN and Ariefiantoro T (2018), which in previous studies produced a positive influence. The inconsistency of this research with previous research means that the indicators in the completion of work depend on the work concept of each individual.

Hypothesis Testing 6: The Influence of Organizational Culture on Performance

The results of the test in table 4 can be seen that the original sample estimate value of organizational culture on performance is 0.369 with a significance of 5% as indicated by the t-statistic value of 1.379 which is smaller than the t-table value of 1.96. Based on these results, the sixth hypothesis is rejected. The results of this study are also not in line with the results of research

The Effect of Motivation and Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction and Their Impact on the Performance of Village Unit Cooperative Employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Indonesia

conducted by M.A.H. Kadir (2017) which results that organizational culture can affect performance. The lack of influence of organizational culture on performance means that in this organization the concept of mutual agreement about the values adopted in organizational life as presented in theory (Siagian, 2014) does not become the basis for achieving employee performance.

Hypothesis Testing 7: The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Performance

The results of the test in table 4 can be seen that the original sample estimate of job satisfaction on performance is 0.267 with a significance of 5%, which is indicated by the t-statistic value of 3.247 which is greater than the t-table value of 1.96. The original sample estimate value is positive which indicates that job satisfaction has a positive effect on performance. Based on these results, the seventh hypothesis is accepted. The positive effect of job satisfaction on performance is in line with the results of research conducted by K Utami (2016) and M. A. H. Kadir (2017) where job satisfaction affects performance. The harmony of this research and previous research means that in accordance with the theoretical concept presented by (Yuki, 2011) where job satisfaction arises when the positive attitude of employees towards the work they face and everything with their work, thus will result in positive performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research in the discussion, it can be said that motivation has a significant effect on job satisfaction, as well as work discipline has a significant effect on job satisfaction but has no effect on performance, then organizational culture has a significant effect on job satisfaction, but has no effect on performance, and job satisfaction. The last one shows a significant effect on the performance of VUC employees in Ogan Komering Ilir Regency. This means that basically permanent employees will provide the best performance results if there is the right motivation. Finally, the author realizes that the results of the research conducted by the author are still quite limited, so the authors hope to be able to conduct further research related to the existing discussion.

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